

COMPARATIVE ETYMOLOGY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article discusses phraseological units, their importance and possibilities in Uzbek and English. Including, opinions are given about some stages of development and features of phraseological units.

Keywords: idiom, fixed combination, etymology, phraseological unit, linguocultur.

Introduction

Phraseological units are of socio-cultural importance and are a means of language that personifies the general image of society, the way of life, traditions. In the study of the English language, it is important to research the linguistic nature of phraseological units, and this problem is considered one of the complex tasks in phraseology.

In linguistics, phraseology appears as a lexical layer that reflects the immeasurable wealth, unlimited possibilities of the language, as well as its specific historical and developmental stages. Until now, certain results have been achieved in the study of the artistic language, methodological feature and lexicon of this rich treasure. Phraseological units, considered a beautiful example of the art of the word, have a significant place in the lexical layer of the language, which means that they, as an artistic means of the language, acquire both significant linguistic and historical significance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

From World linguists in the field of phraseology B.Fraser, N.Khomsky, A.Konin, V.Vinogradov, A.Nazaryan and Uzbek linguists Rahmatullaev,

B.Yuldashev, A.Mamatov, A.Bushoy, M.Sadikovas carried out scientific research work. American scientist B.Fraser believes - " expressions occupy an important place in the field of linguocultural and, unlike simple compounds, they are a hardened compound, the shape and meaning of which are not allowed to change" [6, 22]. Reformatsky, on the other hand, describes – "Phraseological units are combinations of words and phrases characteristic of the speech of different population strata, indicating their class and profession" [3, 128]. According to another linguocultural scientist Chi Ren – "phrases are such a hardened group of words that when their words are taken separately, they will not depend on the general meaning of the phrase."

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Phraseological units should never be understood in denotative terms, that is, words are not used in them with their original meaning, if used in their original meaning it is not considered a phrase. For example;

1. *Little Sarah learnt the alphabet by heart **from A to Z.***
2. *Sarah is an expert in this sphere she knows **from A to Z.** [Authors' examples]*

In the first of the above sentences, words are denotative that is expressed in their original meaning, in the second sentence, words have an additional meaning as a phrase. They can be interpreted in Uzbek as follows:

- 1) Little Sarah memorized the alphabet from A to Z.
- 2) Sarah is an expert in the field she knows it well, from yarn to needle.

In this sentence, an alternative option is the phrase from the thread in Uzbek to the phrase from A to Z in English.

Expressions such as all things and phenomena in the world also have their own history of origin, that is, their etymology. If we study the origin of Phraseological units in a particular language, we will also directly study the history and customs of that nation. There are some words and phrases in English that did not appear

spontaneously in the language, their appearance was caused by some historical event, habit, tradition. We can give many examples of such phrases. For example, *to let the cat out of the bag* - let's pay attention to the history of the origin of the phrase to expose the secret.

In ancient England, a pig was sold at country fairs. It is customary to place the pig in a bag or bag so that the buyer can take his purchase in safety. But then some trickster appears and they bring their bags to the fairs with their mouths connected. A cat will be put into them instead of a pig child. An indifferent buyer returns home with a " pig in a bag", but a cautious buyer requires the seller to open the bag and inspect the pig. It is then that he "exposes the secret" and as a result he "*let the cat out of the bag*", that is, the phrase he exposed the secret appears. [4,106].

For example, if we take the English expression " *bare foot*", which, when translated as a word combination, means " bare feet,without shoes", then as a phrase it means "not yet engaged, single ", and the history of its origin goes back to the end of the Middle Ages. And now let's see why exactly the phrase bare foot is used for a girl who is not yet married. This is due to the fact that in the Middle Ages, relatives who came to visit the girl from the side of the groom presented the future bride with shoes, which is why this very phrase was used. A phrase like this also exists in Uzbek in which it is precisely by saying that the human body organ is empty, nothing, that the girl is not yet married.

Phraseological units with its exact author also exist in English, and such Phraseological units are often found both in oral speech and in written speech, but not everyone is interested in the history of its origin. Taking for example the phrase "on the side of Angels", it is used in the sense of "being a supporter of reality" and its origin goes back to the speech of the British statesman Benjamin Dizraeli in November 1864. Through the use of this phrase, he expressed his opposition to Charles Darwin's opinion in the origin of species that "man is scattered from a

monkey” and said: “Is man an ape or an Angel? Now I am on the side of the Angels ("man is a monkey or an angel? I am an angelic supporter") [6].

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In short, phrases are an important side that makes our language impressive, beautiful. They give a stylistic coloring to the meaning of sentences, that is, it is precisely phrases that can give a meaning that is incapable of giving simple words. Moreover, the way in which they live, worldview, traditions of that people belong can testify even to their history. As can be seen from the above, phrases, that is, Phraseological units are distinguished not only as a folk oral creation, but also by belonging to a specific author's work. It is permissible to note that this serves as a separate research object in the study of the etymological properties of Phraseological units.

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